

Polarographic Determination of Zineb and Maneb

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A polarographic method has been developed for the determination of zineb and mane b in 0.1 M KCl and 2.0 M H₂SO₄ in 40% acetonitrile-formamide (4 : 1) at d.m.e. Each produces well-defined diffusion-controlled reversible anodic waves. The method has been applied for their determination in commercial samples.

Polarography has proved to be an useful tool for the analysis of thio compounds¹. The presence of functional group is responsible for their polarographic behaviour. The present paper deals with the determination of zineb and mane b in commercial samples and food-stuff. A detailed study of polarographic behaviour of these pesticides has been studied in potassium chloride, sulphuric acid and gelatin in 40% acetonitrile : formamide (4 : 1). Budnikov *et al.*² used organic solvents and lithium perchlorate as the electrolyte but in these cases *iR* drop correction has to be applied. In the present study, 40% acetonitrile has been used to overcome these difficulties and potassium chloride has been used as the electrolyte. There is no need to apply the *iR* correction.

Results and Discussion

The concentration of sulphuric acid was varied and it was observed that the diffusion current is constant upto concentration 2.0 M, beyond which it is suppressed. There was very little effect when the concentration of potassium chloride is in the range 0.05–1 M. Polarograms of 0.5 × 10⁻³ M each of zineb and mane b solutions at various heights of the mercury column showed the diffusion-controlled nature of the wave. The values for *i*_d *h*^{-1/2} were found to be fairly constant.

Several polarograms with various concentration of the zineb or mane b were recorded in 0.1 M KCl + 2.0 M H₂SO₄ + 0.005% gelatin. The plots of diffusion current versus concentration were proportional in the range 0.085–0.75 × 10⁻³ and 0.082–0.81 × 10⁻³ M, for zineb and mane b respectively (Table 1). The values of *E*_{1/2} calculated from the plots come out to be -0.18 and -0.188 V for zineb and mane b respectively, versus S.C.E. The mean value of diffusion current constant (*I*) determined from the equation (*I* = *i*_d C⁻¹ m^{-2/3} t^{-1/6}) was found to be 1.515 for zineb and 1.561 for mane b. Applying Lingane equation, *I* = 1.5 *n*, the value of *n* corresponds to one. This suggests the possibility of one electron change,

TABLE 1—RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE DIFFUSION CURRENT AND ZINEB AND MANEB CONCENTRATIONS

Supporting electrolyte : 0.1 M KCl + 2.0 M H₂SO₄, drop time = 3.80s, flow rate of Hg = 2.98 mg s⁻¹, sensitivity = 5X, temp. = 25 ± 1°

Sample	Concn. mM	Diffusion current (μA)*	$I = i_d C^{-1} m^{-2/3} t^{-1/6}$ μA mmol ⁻¹ mg ^{-2/3} s ^{-1/6}
Zineb	0.085	0.333	1.514
	0.34	1.131	1.513
	0.50	1.960	1.515
	0.60	2.353	1.516
	0.75	2.942	1.516
Maneb	0.08	0.333	1.569
	0.28	1.136	1.568
	0.41	1.662	1.567
	0.61	2.446	1.550
	0.81	3.252	1.552

*Corrected for the residual current.

The *E*_{1/2} values were found to be independent of RSH which is characteristic of the above equation.

Commercial samples Dithane Z-78 (active ingredient zineb 75%) and Dithane M-45 (active ingredient mane b 88.3%) were analysed. The results of the determinations are 74% for zineb and 88% for mane b with an RSD of 1.8–2.5%, which are in good agreement with the actual values.

Crop sample (250 g) was taken and zineb or mane b was extracted with acetonitrile (100 ml) and then with acetonitrile (3 × 20 ml). The extract was filtered and evaporated. The residue was dissolved in 5 ml of acetonitrile-dimethylformamide (4 : 1; 5 ml) and determined polarographically as discussed in the procedure above. The recoveries of zineb and mane b were found in the range 97.80–99.13%.

Experimental

Zineb and mane b solutions were prepared in acetonitrile-formamide (4 : 1) and standardised³. The base electrolyte (AnalaR) solutions were prepared in distilled water. Redistilled formamide and acetonitrile were used. Polarograms

were recorded with a Toshniwal ClO_2 polarograph connected to a multiflex galvanometer in conjunction with the dropping mercury electrode, $m = 3.8 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t = 2.98 \text{ s}$. Saturated calomel electrode with KCl bridge was used as the non-polarisable reference electrode.

General procedure : To zineb or maneb solution was added required amounts of the base electrolyte and sulphuric acid and diluted to 20 ml with distilled water and acetonitrile : formamide (4 : 1) to give a 40 ml final solution. It was transferred to the polarographic cell and measurement was made at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ after deaeration.

References

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